

REDUCING USE OF STYRENE MONOMERS IN UNSATURATED POLYESTER RESINS

R. Poillucci¹, C. Hansen¹

¹ Mechanical Engineering, U.Mass Lowell, Lowell MA, USA

* Corresponding author (Christopher_Hansen@uml.edu)

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1 Introduction

Unsaturated polyester resins are commonly used to manufacture fiberglass composites ranging from transportation to consumer products. Most of these resins used are diluted with 35-50 volume percent styrene monomer. Composites manufacturing employees who work with styrenated polyester resins are frequently exposed to vapors and possible physical contact with the styrene monomer, which is classified as a suspected carcinogen, neurotoxin, and respiratory tract irritant by the IARC (International Agency for Research on Cancer) [1]. The aim of this study is to reduce or replace styrene monomer with alternate allyl- and vinyl-based reactive monomer diluents that are substantially less toxic to human health. This hazard reduction-based approach will result in reduced potential for worker exposure to harmful vapors during the manufacturing process.

2 Background

2.1 Polyester Chemistry and Polymerization

Unsaturated polyester resins are a backbone matrix chemistry in composites manufacturing industry. Figure 1 displays a generic unsaturated polyester resin radical polymerization reaction that is initiated via a peroxide, resulting in a crosslinked matrix.

Fig. 1. Crosslink formation within a polyester resin.

The formulation of polyester resin involves dilution of the polyester immediately after the condensation reaction. A typical polyester resin system contains polyesters composed of maleic anhydride and propylene glycol (50-65 wt%), which is then diluted with styrene (35-50 wt%), and then initiated with methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP) (1-2 wt%).

2.2 Driving Forces for Styrene Use in Polyester Resins

Styrene is added to the vast majority of polyester resins and is the reactive monomer of choice due to cost, availability, processing viscosity, and mechanical property considerations. Styrene is inexpensive and available in bulk quantities, such that styrene dilution of polyesters reduces the cost to below half that of higher performance epoxies [2]. Styrene is an excellent diluent to achieve proper processing viscosity for polyester resins. Simple adjustment of the styrene fraction permits wet lay-up with woven textiles, as well as spray-up using a spray gun nozzle and a fiber chopper. Finally, styrenated polyester resins cure at room temperature and exhibit better mechanical properties than observed for alternate monomer diluents [2].

2.3 Existing Efforts to Increase Safety

While styrene is preferred from a standpoint of its engineering performance, styrene usage has multiple associated human health hazards, such as respiratory and skin irritation [3]. Styrene also attacks the central nervous system if exposure persists over a long period of time, leading to possible headaches and depression [4]. The greatest industry concern focuses on the classification of styrene as a carcinogen by IARC [1]. Efforts to address these health hazards focus on either (1) the minimization of styrene volatilization or (2) the elimination of styrene via alternative monomer usage.

In the first approach, styrene is still incorporated into resins but human exposure is minimized by the reduction of monomer volatilization. Paraffin waxes have been added to form a barrier to suppress emissions; however, the wax layer will interfere with adhesion to other parts if not removed prior to bonding [5,6]. A method to reduce the ambient concentration of styrene vapor is to use spray guns that monitor the amount of resin sprayed. This feedback enables employees to not spray excessive quantities of resin, thereby reducing the amount of styrene in the air [7]. The second approach attempts to eliminate exposure to styrene via use of alternate chemistries in polyester resins. Despite the appeal of resins labeled as “non-styrenated”, many of these alternative chemicals possess human health hazards similar to styrene. For example, vinyl toluene has been used to replace styrene [2]; though it is not a known carcinogen, vinyl toluene is strongly irritating to both workers’ skin and respiratory tracts [8]. There is minimal regulatory movement to ban styrene due to its established nature and the lack of viable alternatives. Research has been performed by the organization MNTAP (Minnesota Technical Assistance Program) on current commercially available styrene-free resins. One resin that was investigated is manufactured by NOVOC LLC. Though the resin formulation is proprietary, MNTAP reported that employees working with the non-styrenated resin were exposed to 250-300% greater acetone vapors while exposure to styrene decreased by 17-55%. Performance, however, was 15-25% lower relative to standard styrenated resins on a wide range of metrics, including flexural modulus [7]. Further investigation determined that the resin formulation did not properly impregnate the glass fibers, demonstrating the need to consider specific chemical adhesion factors, as well as increased resin viscosity. The increase in viscosity relative to that of typical industry formulations will likely result in workers’ excess use of resin, thereby not only affecting the mechanical properties but also increasing composite structure costs [7]. Table 1 displays alternative monomers that have been used to replace styrene and the health effects associated with each monomer.

Table 1. Styrene monomer substitutes in commercial formulations

Substitute Monomer	Health Effects
Vinyl Toluene [2, 8]	Affects central nervous system/Respiratory irritant/Skin irritant
Alpha-methylstyrene [9, 10]	Animal carcinogen/Respiratory irritant/Skin irritant
Diallyl phthalate [2, 11]	Possible organ toxicity/Harmful if inhaled/Skin sensitizer

2.4 Material Parameters for Styrene Replacement

In this work, alternative chemicals will be selected according to reduced health risk, low cost, and low mixture viscosity, while retaining the ability to react with the polyester resin. In order to assess the health risks associated with the chemicals a green screen methodology was used. This approach rates various chemicals on a 1 to 4 scale for increasing danger on health effect benchmarks. This method will utilize the approaches used for the globally harmonized system (GHS) [12] and the green screen method [13]. For chemicals that pass the green screen, high priority is placed on chemical cost due to industry reliance on low feedstock prices. The chemicals are then screened by viscosity (μ), which should be comparable to that of styrene (0.68 cP) in order to function as drop-in replacements. Finally, bio-derived chemicals with a lower environmental footprint are given a higher priority. A list of example candidates is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Styrene and Alternate Substitutes

Chemical	Toxicity	Cost (L ⁻¹)	μ (cP)	Material Origin
Styrene	Possible Carcinogen	\$34	0.675	Petroleum
Limonene Oil	Non-Toxic	\$12	0.925	Bio-Derived
Vinyl Neodecanoate	Likely Non-Toxic	\$43	1.1	Petroleum
Vinyl Laurate	Likely Non-Toxic	\$59	0.945	Petroleum

2.5 Polyester Resin Manufacturing Process

Polyester resins are manufactured in large batch reactors. Typical industrial polyester resins are based on phthalic anhydride and maleic anhydride due to their low cost and their excellent yet versatile mechanical properties. The selection of the hydroxyl component is also dominated by cost, as well as reactivity and miscibility; the typical hydroxyl

components used in resins belong to the glycol family, such as propylene glycol and ethylene glycol. It is important to note that glycols also impart a low rate of water absorption, which is important for the marine industry. The dilution of the polyester with styrene monomers while still heated is to prevent crystallization of the polymer component. If the polyester were allowed to cool, it would become a solid and require significant time for re-suspension in monomer. Hence, it is extremely difficult to purchase a commercial polyester without added monomer [2].

2.6 Generating Gradients in Microfluidics

Microfluidic devices are increasingly finding use as a high-throughput method to rapidly screen analytes. Typically, chemical screening of a large range chemical compositions requires robotic deposition of macro-scale samples or the generation of gradients via pipettes that release diffusible substances into a common solvent. This method of gradient generation entails great difficulty to maintain gradients over extended periods of time and requires substantial analyte volumes. Microfluidic gradient devices, by contrast, are able to maintain gradients over hundreds of micrometers while using microliters of analytes [14]. Excellent control over the shape of the gradient has been achieved with as few as two fluidic inlets. The inlet fluids interdiffuse within the hierarchical network, so low flow rates are required in order to form a fully mixed gradient. Equation 1 relates the horizontal width of the fully formed gradient, X , to the diffusion coefficient D and the experimental mixing time T [14].

$$X = \sqrt{2DT} \quad (1)$$

Hence, the residence time of the polyester and alternative monomer analytes in this work must increase quadratically with the width of the microfluidic channel.

3 Experimental

3.1 Approach

The experimental approach to identify suitable styrene alternatives is schematically shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Experimental approach

Alternative monomers to replace styrene are first identified based on containing similar chemical moieties. Next, these chemicals are screened for their human health impacts, which must be minimal. Suitable monomers are then added to unsaturated polyesters to verify miscibility. Fully miscible formulations are polymerized and, if polymerization occurs, DMA samples are fabricated and tested. If the DMA specimen demonstrates performance comparable to commercial resins, a microfluidic device will be used to generate a gradient of DMA specimens with varying polyester to monomer ratios. This method will rapidly screen which polyester-monomer composition will perform best.

3.2 Solubility of Monomers and Polyester

In order to dilute an unsaturated polyester resin, chemicals should be appropriately soluble within the polyester. The solubility of the alternate monomers was initially predicted via solubility parameter calculations and then experimentally verified. The monomer solubility parameters were calculated via the Hansen solubility method. This method calculates the solubility contribution due to dispersion bonds, polar bonds, and hydrogen bonds according to Equations 2 through 4, respectively. F_{di} is the force due to dispersion bonds, F_{pi} is the force due to polar bonds, and E_{hi} is the energy due to hydrogen bonds. V is the molar volume which is calculated based on the molar weight and density of

the respective chemical. Equation 5 calculates the total solubility of the chemical from the individual components [15].

$$\delta_d = \frac{\sum F_{di}}{v} \quad (2)$$

$$\delta_p = \sqrt{\frac{\sum F_{pi}^2}{v}} \quad (3)$$

$$\delta_h = \sqrt{\frac{\sum E_{hi}}{v}} \quad (4)$$

$$\delta = \sqrt{\delta_d^2 + \delta_p^2 + \delta_h^2} \quad (5)$$

If the overall solubility parameter difference ($\Delta\delta$) between a chemical and the polyester of interest is ≤ 5 (MJ/m³)^{1/2}, the two components are predicted as likely to mix. Smaller values of $\Delta\delta$ correspond with an improved likelihood that the chemical and the polyester will be soluble [15].

The calculated solubility parameter and the experimental solubility parameter can be sufficiently divergent that promising candidates were experimentally tested. This approach was performed by mixing a small portion of polyester with a monomer diluent of 30 to 50 volume percent in a 20 mL vial. Compositions that did not readily mix at room temperature were sonicated for 2 hours. In the event that the sample still did not mix, the specimen was sonicated for an additional 2 hours at 60 °C.

3.3 Solubility Results

A sample of a solid, non-diluted polyester was provided by Poliver. The polyester is typically diluted with styrene monomer to obtain a polyester resin. In order to determine if other monomers would be similarly miscible, diluent solubility parameters were calculated and then compared with that of styrene. Though the chemical composition of the polyester was unknown due to proprietary information, monomers similar in value to styrene are likely to be soluble. Monomers with solubility parameters within 5 (MJ/m³)^{1/2} were then mixed in the laboratory to verify their solubility. Trimethylolpropane diallyl ether, which has been previously incorporated into polyester resin formulations was soluble [16]. A summary of experimental results are provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Solubility calculations and mixing results.

Monomer	Calculated Solubility (MJ/m ³) ^{1/2}	Mixing State
Styrene	17.68	Mixed
Limonene	15.27	No mixing
Vinyl Neodecanoate	16.66	No mixing
Trimethylolpropane Diallyl Ether	19.25	Mixed
Trimethylolpropane Diallyl Ether + acetone	N/A	Mixed

Though the trimethylolpropane diallyl ether mixed with the polyester, it possessed an extremely high viscosity. A common method used to modulate the resin viscosity is to add acetone or methanol [7]. Here, the addition of < 1 wt% acetone to the mixture lowered the resin viscosity substantially. The reader is advised to note that the polyester-monomer formulations ultimately required the addition of styrene in order to provide the appropriate mixing and curing, which will be further discussed in the following section.

3.5 Curing Results

The polymerization of miscible solutions composed of 50 wt% monomer and 50 wt% polyester is initiated with the addition of a common peroxide, MEKP (methyl ethyl ketone peroxide). MEKP is added at 2 wt% to each of the solutions and results in a tightly crosslinked structure for styrenated resins (Figure 1). Polymerization results for all of the monomers listed in Table 3 are summarized in Table 4 below. The control specimen with pure styrene monomer cured at room temperature. While the trimethylolpropane diallyl ether mixtures with and without acetone did not cure at room temperature, the solutions polymerized under elevated temperature conditions at 70°C.

Table 4. Curing Results of 50% solution to 50% polyester samples.

Monomer	Percent Styrene in solution %	Temp. (°C)	Cure State
Styrene	100%	21	Cured
Limonene	75%	21	Styrene half cured
Vinyl Neodecanoate	75%	21	Styrene half cured
Trimethylolpropane Diallyl Ether	45%	21	Not cured
Trimethylolpropane Diallyl Ether + acetone	45%	21	Not cured
Trimethylolpropane Diallyl Ether + acetone	45%	70	Cured with an oxygen inhibited layer
Trimethylolpropane Diallyl Ether	45%	70	Cured with an oxygen inhibited layer

3.6 Viscosity Characterization

Viscosity of the polyester resin is of critical importance to the manufacturing of composites. A resin with a high viscosity may clog the nozzle during a spray-up procedure, as well as potentially result in inhomogeneous distribution of the cured matrix. Moreover, elevated viscosity can prevent properly wet out of the reinforcement fiber, as was observed by MNTAP with commercially available styrene-free resin formulations. Alternatively, a resin with an excessively low viscosity may migrate from the initial application location due to gravitational forces. The allyl- and vinyl-based candidate monomers in Table 2 are mixed into an unsaturated polyester resin (Poliver) from 35 to 50 wt% for viscosity observations. The diluent composition for each monomer choice is also varied between pure candidate monomer to pure styrene monomer in steps of ~25% to obtain a viscosity near 500 cP. Candidate compositions are first narrowed based on simple visual observations of viscosity. Mixtures with sufficiently low viscosity are subsequently

measured under stress-controlled conditions on a rheometer (TA Ares G2) fitted with a cone and plate geometry.

3.7 Manufacturing of Polyester

The solubility and polymerization results shown above in Tables 3 and 4 are relatively poor. The results indicate that for the Poliver polyester, the mixture requires at least 50 wt% diluent and that at least 50% of this diluent must be styrene to achieve suitably low viscosity. Though the styrene content is reduced by half, other polyesters may offer a route to full elimination of styrene content via improved chemical compatibility. Because no alternative commercial non-styrenated sources of polyesters were found, an effort to manufacture polyester resin in the laboratory setting is made. Maleic anhydride and phthalic anhydride are typically used in industry, so translation of results to commercial use would be easier for similarly based polyester resins. For this reason and reasons of reactivity and ultimate mechanical properties, maleic anhydride is chosen. The selection of the hydroxyl component focused on ethylene glycol and propylene glycol due to the combination of their good reactivity and low cost. Ethylene glycol is more hazardous than propylene glycol due to the greater reactivity of the primary hydroxyl groups in polyethylene glycol relative to the secondary hydroxyl groups in polypropylene glycol. Moreover, propylene glycol can be derived from biological sources, such as corn-starch [17]. These toxicity and sourcing factors led to the use of propylene glycol in the polyester resin. The polyester resin is manufactured by a stoichiometric reaction with equivalent molar quantities of propylene glycol and maleic anhydride, which are mixed inside a round bottom flask. The flask is heated in silicone oil to heat the reaction to 150 to 180°C. The water produced by the reaction is removed via a water-chilled condenser schematically shown in Figure 5. The water vapor from the reaction migrates to the water evaporation tube and then condenses to a liquid. This water removal process is maintained for 12+ hours to drive the condensation reaction polymers to higher molecular weight.

Fig. 5. Experimental setup for manufacturing polyester.

After the chemicals are sufficiently reacted to produce long-chain polyesters, the solution is purified. Acetone, in which the polyester and unreacted monomers are soluble, is used to suspend the polymer in solution for removal from the round bottom flask. The solution is then diluted with methanol, which induced precipitation of the polyester while the unreacted monomers are retained in the supernatant. The supernatant is removed and the purification step is repeated for a total of three times. The resulting purified polyester is crystallized on the container bottom, from where it is recovered for further study and dilution with alternatives to styrene monomer.

4 Microfluidic Screening of Chemical Compositions

4.1 Screening of Alternative Chemistries via Microfluidics for Mechanical Characterization

Styrene alternatives must satisfy stiffness and ultimate strength requirements for typical composite applications. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) will be used to characterize mechanical properties of various matrix compositions. For chemistries identified as promising candidates in the initial stages of this work, a range of compositions of monomer to polyester are mixed within microfluidic channels. Specifically, composition A and composition B are displaced from syringes via a syringe pump set to a constant flow rate through a microfluidic device similar to the schematic seen in Figure 6. The fluids flow and diffusively mix under laminar conditions to result in a range of predictable polyester resin compositions, which subsequently fill cavities that correspond to specimen dimensions for DMA. This will allow various ratios of monomer

to polyester to be screened simultaneously. In order to verify the percentage of each chemical mixing in a channel flow, visualization tests are performed using water dyed with rhodamine 6G and yellow-yellow-green with fluorescein (Sigma-Aldrich). The microfluidic channels are 500 μm in width and are fabricated by CNC (computer numerical control) micro-milling from a plate of acrylic. The patterned plate is then bonded to a neat acrylic block to encapsulate the microfluidic network.

Fig. 6. Schematic of microfluidic device to create a gradient of DMA specimen compositions.

After the diffusively mixed composite matrix samples are cured, they will be removed and require dimensioning for DMA. The specimens are post-processed by polishing with successively increasing fine polishing papers (320, 400, 600 grit), and calipers are used to verify the width is sufficiently constant over the length of the flexural specimens.

4.2 Microfluidic Results

A microfluidic device was successfully fabricated to assess mixing conditions for fluid flows. The diffusive mixing was observed via input fluid compositions dyed yellow and red (Figure 7) that subsequently split and recombine. The fluid compositions within the five channels shown in Figure 7b increase linearly in red-dye content from 0% (left) to 100% (right).

Fig 7. Fluorescein- (left) and rhodamine-dyed (right) water inputs flow at 0.05 mL/min and diffusively mix. (a) View of third generation flow split. (b) View of mixed compositions at device exit.

The liquid flow rate must be maintained below approximately 1 mL/min in order to achieve full diffusive mixing within this microfluidic geometry. Above this flow rate, the parallel streams have insufficient time to fully mix within each generation of channels prior to bifurcation at the channel end for each generation of the network. Flows of polyester resin mixtures demonstrate similar behavior, though the concomitant decrease in diffusion with increased viscosity requires further reduction in flow rates. Flow rates were varied from 0.05 mL/min to 0.20 mL/min in increments of 0.05 mL/min. The best diffusive mixing was observed at 0.05 mL/min, indicating that higher flow rates may require narrower network channels.

5 Conclusions and Future Directions

Alternative monomers to styrene have been identified for use in polyester resins based on reduced toxicity, viscosity as related to processing parameters, and cost. The identified monomers were mixed into a commercially available polyester. Though the monomers demonstrated limited chemical compatibility, styrene content was reduced by 50% with trimethylolpropane diallyl ether. Future work will continue to synthesize polyester from maleic anhydride and polypropylene glycol to identify improved chemical solubilities. A gradient network microfluidic device was fabricated and successfully used to generate five polymer matrix compositions for rapid screening. In continuing work, DMA specimens will be created from these solutions to create a library of resin formulations and their associated mechanical properties. These resins will then be used to impregnate textiles either in situ or ex situ with respect to the microfluidic devices.

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